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The adults as English learners

Abstract

Vocabulary and spelling are two of the most important skills to achieve success in an academic setting. This review of 15 articles highlights classroom interventions that successfully enhanced vocabulary and spelling skills among ESL, English Only, English language learners (ELL), and learning-disabled (LD) students. The strategies that enhanced vocabulary skills were reading strategies, storybook reading strategies, and memorization strategies. The strategies that enhanced spelling skills were Cover, Copy, and Compare (CCC) and writing strategies. Results showed that the strategy of storybook reading enhanced the vocabulary skills among both English Only and ESL students. Writing strategies resulted in spelling skill improvement for students with LD. Future research should focus on the CCC strategy application to improve their vocabulary skills for ESL students who also have LD.

Key words

Strategies, vocabulary, spelling, learning disabilities, English as a second language, English-Only, reading strategies

INTRODUCTION

Among the thousands of languages spoken around the world, English has become the primary global language of the 21st century. As one of the most widely distributed languages, native and second language speakers in great number use English internationally. English is the main language of communication in international diplomatic relations Crystal (2003). Two of the most important components of learning English are spelling and vocabulary. Wilkins (1972) summed up the importance of vocabulary by writing, “while without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed” (pp. 111–112). Similarly, Jaspers et al. (2012) remarked on the important relationship between spelling and learning English.

Vocabulary and Spelling It is necessary to briefly lay out what is meant in the current paper by the terms “vocabulary” and “spelling.” Vocabulary can be defined as the words of a language, including “single items and phrases or chunks of several words which convey a particular meaning, the way individual words do” (Lessard-Clouston, 2013, para. 2). These lexical chunks include such phrases as “good morning” and “nice to meet you” and they are

the key to communication and developing student skills (Sánchez & Manchón, 2007). The stronger students' vocabularies are, the more complex material they will use that will benefit them, allowing them to communicate and understand others much better. A student's understanding of a vocabulary word's meaning and usage (depth) can vary from shallow (merely recognizing a word and/or using that word in a basic way) to deep use (ability to use the word in a multitude of contexts) (Carlo et al., 2004).

Challenges of Learning English

The English language is complex to learn because often times it can be challenging to spell a word correctly and use it in a sentence properly. If an adult is able to spell, recognize, and use a word in the proper format written and verbally, then the adult has mastered that word. According to Cook (1999), the true goal of the English writing system reaches beyond spelling and pronunciation in communication and the final test is whether meaning can be conveyed and understood. English can be tricky because there are many words that sound the same when pronounced but are spelled differently and, therefore, have a completely different meaning. For example, the words rain, rein, and reign all have very different meanings but all sound the same and may be a point of confusion for a user of English vocabulary. Because the English language is complex to master, the best way for a person to achieve true understanding, according to Plester, Wood, & Joshi (2009), is to establish a connection between reading comprehension and spelling. The path to reading and writing fluently in English "is through mastering the connections between letter combinations and the sounds they represent" (Joshi & Roth, 2009, p.1).

Adults who have LD are more likely to struggle with learning English, even in their native language, compared to their peers (Schwarz et al., 2000). Additionally, students with LD can be weaker in their understanding of syntax, grammar, and vocabulary, which makes learning spelling and vocabulary challenging (Cortiella & Horowitz, 2014). Similarly, ESL adults with LD tend to be weaker in their native language as well (across the areas of writing, reading, comprehension, and spelling abilities), which makes learning a foreign language like English even more challenging (Ipek, 2009). Typically, to learn a foreign language such as English, a student relies on his/her knowledge of their native syntax, grammar, and sentence structure to help make sense of the foreign language he/she is trying to learn (Sparks et al., 2008). However, ESL students with LD are at a disadvantage and would benefit from language-building strategies, especially in the areas of spelling accuracy and vocabulary acquisition (Carter et al., 2013 & Schwarz, 2000). Because LD students learn best through multi-sensory, direct, intensive tactile/kinesthetic, visual, and auditory instruction (Cortiella & Horowitz, 2014), one would hope to find vocabulary and spelling strategies in the literature that utilize these learning pathways.

Vocabulary Strategies

In order to help students build their vocabulary skills, researchers have used a variety of strategies including direct reading instruction strategies, storybook reading strategies, and

memorization strategies. The direct instruction strategies included direct word instruction (Carlo et al., 2004), and Cover, Copy, Compare (CCC) (Carter et al., 2013).

The storybook reading strategies included listening to stories (Brett et al., 1996), video stories (short story) (Chun & Plass, 1996), home storybook reading (Roberts, 2008), and reading and retelling stories (Joe, 1998). Memorization strategies, like the Keyword strategy (Brown & Perry, 1991) and Kramersch's procedure strategy (Faraj, 2015), have also assisted students' vocabulary retention.

Direct instruction

Direct instruction in vocabulary appears to help students increase their vocabulary and fluency (Yildirim et al., 2014). In the CCC study by Carlo et al. (2004), adult ELL students learned 100 to 120 target words each week over 15 weeks. This CCC study teaches spelling by having students look at each spelling word, cover the word, copy the word down based on how they remembered the spelling, and then compare what they wrote to the actual spelling of the word. The practice is repeated until the student masters the spelling of each word. Carlo et al. (2004) used "word mastery" as the measure for intervention. In Carlo et al.'s (2004) study, reading comprehension skills increased to 80% when students were provided with the CCC approach to learning spelling, which led to learning new vocabulary. Improved vocabulary increases reading comprehension. In a second study by Carter et al. (2013), participants were three 25-year-old ESL and LD reading students who learned 25 new words over the course of one week, in three

25-minute periods. The students were taken into a resource setting and given the set of words to learn at the first intervention. The teacher taught the spelling as direct instruction, and the students practiced alongside the teacher. Then, as independent practice, the students used the CCC strategy to track their own progress. The three students did increase their vocabulary skills as a result of the intervention. Carter et al.

(2013) used the measurements (word mastery) when reviewing target words. Direct word instruction was found to be effective at increasing vocabulary skills with ELL learners. In addition, the intervention was found to improve student fluency by 50%. In fact, vocabulary acquisition with these strategies (i.e. direct word instruction and CCC) was found to be related to other skills, such as reading fluency and comprehension (Carlo et al., 2004, Carter et al., 2013).

Conclusion

It seems that, in spite of the difficulties that might occur, the process of teaching English to adult learners can prove to be very interesting and, at the same time, rewarding. These learners' motivation, determination and life experience can bring a wide range of benefits to the context of instruction. However, it is obvious that instructors must be more flexible and more responsive in adult educational contexts. It is only in this way that teachers can really contribute to the success of their students' learning by creating a positive climate

which makes adults feel emotionally safe, and which offers them the type of instruction that they expect.

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